

Safety Management System Implementation Analysis, Occupational Health (OHSMS) in the Department of Communications, Informatics, Commanding and Statistics, Serang District

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Abstract:- The K3 management system is a part of the company's overall management system in controlling risks related to work activities in order to create a safe, productive and efficient workplace. SMK3 in its role in reducing the risk of work accidents can also affect employee performance. This can be seen if a work accident occurs, the work targets within the service will be hampered. The aim of this research is to determine the level of implementation of the Occupational Safety and Health Management System (SMK3), determine the factors that cause the implementation of the Occupational Safety and Health Management System (SMK3) to be incomplete, and take action to ensure compliance with the implementation of the Occupational Safety and Health Management System. (SMK3) at DISKOMINFOSATIK Kab. Serang according to statutory regulations. In this research, the method applied is qualitative research using NVivo software analysis tools. This research obtained results in the form of a 4 stage strategy, namely formulation, implementation of the K3 system, evaluation and corrective action for SMK3. At the formulation stage there were 4 aspects that the researcher concentrated on, namely disposition, bureaucratic structure, reporting and resources. The implementation is then scrutinized through interviews with key informants and followed by evaluation so that suggestions for corrective action can be obtained for existing management..

Keywords:- K3 Management System, DISKOMINFOSATIK, Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Implementing occupational safety and health with OHSMS or SMK3 has evolved in developed countries both through standards and the basis for its implementation. Based on PP No. 50 of 2012, occupational safety and health (OHS or K3) are all activities to ensure and protect the safety and health of workers through efforts to prevent work accidents and work-related health problems.

Based on data published by the Indonesian Ministry of Manpower (KEMNAKER) in 2020, as many as 57.5% of the total 126.51 million working population in Indonesia have a low level of education. Based on this, it is indicated that low

education results in low worker awareness of the importance of implementing occupational safety and health (K3) culture.

In Law No. 1 of 1970 concerning occupational safety and health, it is not only applied in industry but must also be applied in offices. Considering the importance of implementing K3, useful facilities and infrastructure are also needed to support the implementation of K3 in various lines of companies in Indonesia. Regarding K3 implementation factors, it is also necessary to implement the use of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) as a form of prevention against worker errors which can result in fatal consequences of errors that occur.

Data on work accidents in Indonesia is actually still filled with many mysteries regarding the actuality or accuracy of the data published, considering the extent and number of regions and islands owned by the Indonesian state, the data that is widely reviewed and is the basis for the K3 condition in Indonesia is data that is coming from the Social Security Administering Agency (BPJS) for employment, through the official page of the BPJS for employment, we were informed that JKK provides guaranteed protection against risk accidents that occur while working. Companies in Indonesia are also required to always report K3 in an actual and fast manner if an incident occurs in their company with a maximum reporting duration of 2 x 24 hours after the incident occurs..

Based on data obtained from the National K3 month speech and BPJS TK data, in 2018-2021 there was no data related to work-related deaths, so if you look at the trend, the interval is 2%, from this it can be estimated that work-related deaths are in the range of 3,000-4,500 deaths each year. From this graph, it can be seen that in 2020 there was a significant increase in cases of work accidents and deaths, this is thought to be the result of the COVID-19 pandemic that hit throughout 2020. In 2021 there was a drastic decline in cases of work accidents and deaths, p. This is also thought to be the effect of the resolution of the COVID-19 case in Indonesia and the many companies implementing the work from home (WFH) system and even temporarily closing their companies.

The Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) states that in an effort to reduce the number of accident victims that occur in industry, accident cases that

occur in an industry must be designated as a case of criminal business for which employees and managers of the company must be held accountable. Providing more attention and empathy towards safety and health in the workplace is a must for company owners and their management in order to create a healthy and safe work environment for employees in their company. In fact, there are still many work accidents occurring, even several cases that cause death or physical disability for workers, this is caused by the lack of role of

company owners and their management in paying attention to occupational health and safety in the company as well as the lack of knowledge of employees regarding their rights. in occupational safety and health. From this, the implementation of an occupational safety and health management system becomes one of the main things in a company because it can have a negative impact both in terms of the legality of the company and in terms of employee performance.

Tabel 1 OSHA Inspection Statistics

OSHA Inspection Statistics	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Total Inspections	31,948	32,408	32,023	33,393	21,710	24,333
Total Programmed Inspections	12,731	14,377	13,956	14,900	8,729	10,584
Total Unprogrammed Inspections	19,217	18,031	18,067	18,493	12,981	13,749
Fatality/Catastrophe Inspections	890	837	941	919	1,498	1,386
Complaints Inspection	8,870	8,249	7,489	7,391	4,592	4,955
Referrals	6,691	6,286	6,463	6,718	4,810	5,310
Other Unprogrammed Inspections	2,766	2,659	3,174	3,465	2,081	2,098

Sumber; OSHA inspection statistic 2021

From the table above obtained from OSHA inspections statistics, it can be seen that there was an increase in the number of inspections related to the number of work accidents from 2016 to 2019, which then decreased in 2020 and then increased again in 2021, in 2021 it is indicated that there were 24,333 inspections that occurred where there were a total of 13,749 inspections that had not been programmed related to OHS, this was equivalent to 43% of the total inspections that had been carried out.

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Implementation standards governing SMK3 are contained in Government Regulation No. 50 2012 which applies nationally and is mandatory if the company operates in the territory of the Republic of Indonesia, and international standards are regulated in ISO 45001 and OHSAS 18001, as standards that are trusted internationally. internationally by all countries.

Occupational Health and Safety Assessment Series - 18001 (OHSAS) is an international standard for an occupational health and safety management system. OHSAS 18001 has objectives that coincide with the Ministry of Manpower's SMK3. In this case OHSAS also operates in protecting workers against unexpected things while they are working which will affect work safety and health which in turn will have a negative impact on the company both from external impacts such as tarnishing the good name of the company itself and from its own internal factors. in the form of a decrease in work productivity figures which results in reduced profits that the company should get.

➤ *In Implementing a Standard in the Implementation of OHSAS 18001, there are Several main Components and Factors that must be met First, Including:*

- Commitment from all levels of company management in carrying out occupational safety and health (K3) management
- Carry out planning and analysis of the SMK3 Program
- Implement and run SMK3
- Make corrections and evaluate the implementation of the K3 management system
- Conduct a review of company management regarding the application and implementation of SMK3 policies so that they can run continuously.

➤ *In Carrying out Preparation in Accordance with OHSAS Provisions, there are Seven Stages, Including:*

- Identify risks starting from the smallest things and their impacts and dangers on the environment
- Make adjustments and implement the provisions of the Law and applicable legal regulations
- Determine company targets in implementing the program
- Implementing it for all company components
- Develop plans to anticipate emergency incidents during operational processes
- Review implementation targets
- Implement policies related to OHSAS

The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) is an organization that standardizes everything that has measurements in setting its standards, in terms of standardization related to SMK3 ISO issues a standard in the form of ISO 45001 with the aim of reducing the number of potential risks that can cause death or disability of members. body, which is directly related to the operational activities of an organization or company.

In regional regulation No. 11 th. 2016 which regulates the structure and organization of the district's regional apparatus. Serang, then received changes to Regional Regulation No. 10 of 2018, in these changes there were the addition of several additional regional organizations within the Serang Regency government, one of these additions included the addition of the Department of Communication and Informatics, Statistics and Cryptography (DISKOMINFOSATIK), tasked with implementing government affairs in the fields of Communication, Informatics, Statistics and coding.

DISKOMINFOSATIK, if seen from the time of its formation, is one of the services that is still quite new but has a quite vital role in terms of technological developments which continue to grow and the need for social media which is the face of all government agencies towards the communities they cover, as well as today's need for facilities and infrastructure that are much needed by both government offices and the public regarding the provision of internet-related services.

In meeting these internet-related needs, the Serang Regency DISKOMINFOSATIK continues to do its best to build infrastructure both within the scope of the Regional Apparatus Organization (OPD) and for communities throughout the Serang Regency area, looking at the geological map. Serang Regency still has many villages and areas that are consists of villages, but this is not an obstacle for the Serang Regency government to continue providing services, especially in internet infrastructure.

On this basis, the author wants to examine further, Analysis of the implementation of Occupational Safety and Health at DISKOMINFOSATIK Serang District. So the problem formulation is obtained as follows:

- How good is the level of SMK3 implications in the analysis of the implementation of Occupational Safety and Health at DISKOMINFOSATIK Serang District?
- What factors cause the implications of implementing SMK3 not to be fulfilled in the analysis of the implementation of Occupational Safety, Health at the Communication, Cryptography Information and Statistics Department of Serang Regency?
- How to improve the response to ensure fulfillment of SMK3 implications in the Analysis of the implementation of Occupational Safety and Health at DISKOMINFOSATIK Serang District?
- Can the implementation of the Occupational Safety and Health Management System (SMK3) in the Analysis of Occupational Safety, Health and Safety implementation in the Communications, Coding Information and Statistics Service of Serang Regency affect employee performance?

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ SMK3

Based on PP no. 50 Years 2012, SMK3 is a component of the overall management system of the company in terms of risk management related to work performance in order to create a pleasant, not only productive but also efficient work environment. K3 includes all actions that ensure and protect all workforce through efforts to prevent accidents and work-related diseases.

➤ Implementation of K3 Policy

Increasing the learning and development mechanism that is necessary to reach a particular milestone is an effective way to implement K3 policies. K3 goals and objectives in a particular work environment must be integrated with the management system of the company that already exists. Some things the industry needs to be aware of here:

- Capability Types
- Human, physical, and financial summaries
- Complementary
- Responsibility and accountability
- Consulting, motivation and skills
- Support and Action
- Communication
- Report
- Records
- paperwork control
- Operations management recording
- Identify sources of danger & risk management
- Identify sources of danger
- Risk assessment
- Control measures
- Planning and engineering
- Administrative control
- Doing contract review
- Purchase
- Emergency or disaster response procedures
- Procedures for dealing with incidents
- Recovery plan procedures
- Measurement and Evaluation
- Inspection and testing
- SMK3 Audit
- Corrective and preventive actions
- Review by Management
- Assessment on work-related injuries, occupational health, and environmental conditions
- Goals, targets and performance for safety, occupational health and the environment
- Goals, targets and work safety, workplace health, and environment
- Evaluation of the effectiveness of implementing SMK3L and the need to revise SMK3 so that it is appropriate will:
- Revise the rules
- Feedback from related parties and vendors
- Product improvement and change management activities
- Organizational structure of the company

- The advancement of knowledge and technology includes epidemiology.
- Experience gained from occupational safety and health incidents
- Report
- Feedback especially from the workforce.

➤ *Labor Protection*

According to Law Number 13 of 2003 concerning Manpower, Article 86 paragraph (1) states that every worker has the right to physical protection, including protection from work accidents:

- Occupational Health and Safety
- Morals and decency; And
- Treatment that is in accordance with dignity and religious values.

The workforce is protected to increase production and productivity by performing their work safely.

➤ *The Work Environment*

Low potential, whether originating from outside or within the surrounding environment, comes from the manufacturing process (construction), which includes raw materials, products or final results. Conditions of the work area, temperature, humidity, humidity, air, and lighting are some aspects of the work environment (ILO, 2013).

Unsafe Condition is when there are tools, materials or environments in the workplace that are dangerous. Examples of these conditions include slippery floors, broken or fractured stairs, lack of lightning in places, and sound beyond safe limits (Ramli, 2010). Unsafe situations can be caused by many of the following:

- Equipment is no longer suitable for use
- Non-standard security
- Exposure to excessive noise and radiation
- Insufficient/excessive lighting
- System for excessive warnings.

➤ *Foundation for SMK3 Implications*

Basically, implementing SMK3 depends on the risk level and is related to the operating process and production existing in the work environment. The higher the level of work accident risk, the more intensive the implementation of SMK3 will be to make the work environment and workplace safer, healthier and more productive (Tarwaka, 2014). Every company must comply with PP no. 50 years. 2012 regarding the implications of SMK3..

➤ *Determination of K3 Policy*

A company can use and implement K3 policies in accordance with seven requirements, namely:

- In accordance with the characteristics and level of organizational risk
- Committed to continuous improvement

- Committed to comply with applicable K3 provisions and other requirements that have been determined by the organization
- Document, implement, and deploy throughout the organization
- Provide understanding to all workers about the aims and objectives of the K3 policy
- Connect with other related parties; And
- Conduct regular reviews to ensure that it remains relevant and appropriate to the organization

Government Regulation no. 50 of 2012 concerning Implementation of Occupational Safety and Health Management Systems (SMK3) regulates company K3 policies, including:

- The K3 policy must be made in writing, dated and signed by the management. This policy includes the company's vision, goals, commitment, work program and covers all company activities. Company policies must always be evaluated or reviewed to improve K3 performance.
- Provide adequate resources for top management's commitment to K3, which is shown in the form of:

- ✓ Position of the K3 organization strategic
- ✓ A clear budget to support labor and the K3 sector
- ✓ Clear responsibilities, authority and obligations for workers d) Coordinated K3 planning and K3 performance assessment

- Company's K3 condition: Initial review is carried out in the following way:

- ✓ Make comparisons based on applicable provisions (SMK3 guidelines) by identifying existing conditions in an effort to ensure compliance with applicable laws and regulations.
- ✓ Check and identify workplace hazards
- ✓ Improve evaluation of compliance with statutory regulations and K3 requirements
- ✓ Checking the causes and as a result of dangerous events, accident compensation, and disruption
- ✓ K3 assessment analysis based on previous findings
- ✓ Make an evaluation of the effectiveness and efficiency of the resources that have been provided.

➤ *Planning K3*

- *The Preparation of K3 Plans for Entrepreneurs must be based on:*

- ✓ Results of the first investigation
- ✓ Identification of possible dangers, assessment and risk management
- ✓ Laws and additional conditions
- ✓ Resources available

K3 experts, the K3 Advisory Committee, worker/labor representatives, and other related parties must be involved by employers when making K3 plans.

- *The K3 Plan made by the Smallest Company Includes:*

- ✓ Goals and objectives
- ✓ Priority time
- ✓ Efforts to control sources of danger
- ✓ Resource assignment
- ✓ Time required to complete activities. Indicators of achievement of the responsibility system

- *Implementation of K3 Planning*

Referring to the implementation of the K3 plan and supported by human resource infrastructure and facilities in the field of human resources, companies must have:

- Job Competition Certificate;
- Proven by a work/operation permit and/or appointment letter from the authorized agency with K3 authority; and The facilities and infrastructure in question are as follows:
 - 1) Organization or unit responsibility for safety and health (K3) issues
- Adequate budget
- Information and reporting on operational/work procedures and documentation
- There are work incentives.
- To fulfill the requirements that an entrepreneur must do the least, he must do the following:
 - *Carry out control measures*
 - *Planning and engineering*
 - *Work procedures and work instructions*
 - *Submission of part of the work implementation*
 - *Purchase or procurement of goods and services*
 - *Final product*
 - *Make efforts to deal with emergency accidents*
 - *There is a plan and emergency recovery. Entrepreneurs must:*
 - There are human resources with appropriate expertise, competence and authority in the field of K3..
 - Involvement of employee.
 - Every employee in the company and other related parties must comply with the K3 instructions that have been created and compiled.
 - Create and compile information procedures.
 - Establish reporting procedures that include:

Reporting workplace accidents, non-compliance with applicable regulations or standards, K3 performance, identification of sources of danger, and reporting based on legislation. Finally, documentation of all steps must at a minimum include: a) K3 regulations and standards; b) performance metrics; c) Work permit; d) Results of risk identification, assessment and control; e) K3 control actions; f) Inspection, calibration and maintenance activities; g) Data monitoring records; h) Results of work accident investigations and follow-up actions; i) Product identification, including its composition; j) information regarding suppliers and contractors k) audit and review of SMK3

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- Job Competition Certificate;
- Proven by a work/operation permit and/or appointment letter from the authorized agency with K3 authority; and The facilities and infrastructure referred to are as follows:
 - Organization or unit responsibility for safety and health issues (K3)
 - Adequate budget
 - Information and reporting regarding operational/work procedures and documentation
 - There are work incentives.
 - To ensure that they meet the requirements that employers do at least, they must do things according to standards.

- *Monitoring and Evaluation of K3 Performance*

Overseas and K3 performance evaluation carried out by the company includes the following:

- Inspections, Tests and Measurements must be established and maintained in accordance with K3 goals and objectives, and with a frequency that is in accordance with applicable regulations and standards.
- SMK3 Internal Audit

It must be carried out regularly to evaluate the effectiveness of implementing SMK3, and must be carried out independently and systematically by staff who have the ability to use the established methodology. Audit results should be evaluated based on evidence of workplace hazard sources and a review of previous audit results. The results of monitoring and evaluating performance and auditing of SMK3 must be communicated and used to take preventive and corrective actions. Monitoring, evaluating and auditing SMK3 performance ensures that management implements it in an orderly and efficient manner.

- *Review and Improvement of SMK3 Performance*

Employers and/or company or workplace administrators must do the following to ensure that SMK3 is appropriate and effective to achieve its objectives:

- Conduct regular reviews;
- The OHSMS review must include the implications of K3 for various activities, products and services, as well as their impact on company performance.

- *Assessment of the Implementation of the Occupational Safety and Health Management System (SMK3)*

Assessment of the implementation of SMK3, also known as audit, is a systematic and independent examination of the fulfillment of standards that have been set to measure the results of actions that have been planned and implemented in the implementation of the Occupational Safety and Health Management System (SMK3) in the company (Permenaker, 2014).

According to PP No.50 of 2012, article 16 paragraph (3), assessment of the implementation of SMK3 is carried out through an SMK3 audit which includes: a. Development and security of commitment implementation; b. Creation and documentation of SMK3 plans; c. Termination of contract design and review; d. Document control; e. Purchasing and controlling products; f. Security works based on SMK3; g. Monitoring standards; h. Reporting and correcting deficiencies; i.

➤ *Objectives and Benefits of Audits in the Implementation of the Occupational Safety and Health Management System (SMK3)*

According to Article 2 of PP No.50 of 2012, the aim of implementing a Work Safety and Safety System (SMK3) is to implement an K3 system in the workplace that involves integrated elements of management, labor, working conditions and work environment to prevent and reduce work accidents and their consequences. with the aim of creating a safe, efficient and productive work environment. Specifically, the objectives of the SMK3 audit are as follows:

- Assess thoroughly and systematically the possible dangers associated with the production process or work process in the workplace or work environment.
- Ensure that the company implements work safety policies in accordance with statutory regulations and company policies.
- Find accidents and losses to company assets.

The benefits of audits carried out for system implementation. One of the objectives of Occupational Health and Safety Management (K3) is as follows: 1. Management can identify weaknesses in operational system components before accidents, mishaps or other losses occur.

- Can get a clear and complete picture of K3 performance which has been implemented by the company.

- Increase compliance with K3 laws and regulations.
- Can increase work productivity by increasing K3 knowledge, skills and awareness, especially for employees involved in carrying out audits.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

➤ *Research Paradigm*

In this research, the positivism paradigm is applied. positivism views a reality, symptom or phenomenon as something that can be classified, concrete, observable, measurable, relatively fixed, and has a cause-and-effect relationship. Quantitative research which is based on the empiricist understanding of positivism sees that truth is in facts that can be proven or empirically tested. This research elaborates on three important points to gain a deeper understanding.

➤ *Research Design/Strategy*

The research method used in this research is a quantitative approach. Quantitative methods are called traditional methods, because this method has been used for a long time. This method is called a new method because it has not been popular for a long time, it is called a postpositivistic method because it is based on the philosophy of postpositivism. Quantitative research stated by (Nana Syaodih, 2010) emphasizes objective phenomena and is studied quantitatively. Research strategies with quantitative designs always involve a post-positivist view. The aim of quantitative research is to look for relationships between variables such as in survey research or to compare samples related to research results.

➤ *Concept definition*

In this research, several concepts are used to explain and focus the problem to be studied. As follows:

Table 2 Concept Definition

Variables	Concept Definition	Technique Data Collection	Indicator
Aspects of Bureaucratic Structure			
Management Integrated	K3 management is integrated with comprehensive company management	Interview Observation	
Procedures & Work Instructions	There are references/guidelines and work instructions that take into account K3 requirements	Observation Document Interview	SOP and legal regulations
Disposition Aspect			
K3 Commitment	There is an K3 commitment stated in writing and signed by the appointed management	Document Interview	Company K3 policy
Awareness	Workers play an active role in supporting the achievement of SMK3 goals and objectives	Interview Observation	Using PPE, work according to SOP,
Resource Aspect			
Human Resources	Placing personnel with clear responsibilities, authority and obligations in handling K3 who have Work Competencies in the K3 field.	Interview	Work/Operation Permit and/or Letter of Appointment from the authorized agency.
Infrastructure	Consists of organizations/units responsible for K3 & a budget is available for implementation	Observation Interview	supporting facilities & infrastructure K3 implementation

Training	There is training held to improve work competency in the field of K3 Implementation	Document Interview	
Risk Management & Emergency Response Management	Implementation of hazard identification, risk assessment & control measures as well as procedures for dealing with incidents, emergency response & emergency recovery.	Observation Document Interview	In accordance with statutory regulations
Reporting aspect			
Reporting	There is reporting of K3 activities, including accident reports	Document Interview	

➤ *Social Situation*

This research was conducted in the Serang Regency Communication, Informatics, Coding and Statistics Office, which is the center for key informants.

➤ *Key Informant*

Research informants are parties who have the authority and knowledge regarding ANALYSIS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY, HEALTH MANAGEMENT SYSTEM (SMK3) IN THE DEPARTMENT OF COMMUNICATIONS, INFORMATICS, CODING AND STATISTICS OF SERANG DISTRICT. The human element as an instrument is the researcher who is directly involved in participatory observation and the informant element is described in the following table:

Table 3 List of Key Informants

NO	ACTIVITY	ACTOR	PLACE
1	Head of the DISKOMINFOSATIK	Informan	DISKOMINFOSATIK office
2	Secretary of DISKOMINFOSATIK	Informan	DISKOMINFOSATIK office
3	Head of Telematics Division	Informan	DISKOMINFOSATIK office
4	KASUBAG program	Informan	DISKOMINFOSATIK office
5	Telematika Staff	Informan	DISKOMINFOSATIK office

➤ *Sampling Method*

The research method used in this research is snow ball sampling. Snowball sampling or chain reference sampling is defined as a non-probability sampling technique where the sample has characteristics that are rarely found. This is a sampling technique, where existing subjects provide references to recruit the sample required for a research study.

In the ANALYSIS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY, HEALTH (SMK3) MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN THE SERANG DISTRICT COMMUNICATIONS, INFORMATICS, AND STATISTICS DEPARTMENT, this sampling method involves primary data sources nominating other potential data sources who will be able to participate in the research study. The Snowball Sampling method is purely reference based and that is how a researcher can generate a sample. Therefore, this method is also called the chain-referral sampling method.

This sampling technique can go on continuously, like a snowball that gets bigger and bigger (in this case the sample size) until the researcher has enough data to analyze, to draw conclusive results that can help the organization make the right decisions.

The nature of Snowball Sampling is such, that it cannot be considered for a representative sample or in that case for a statistical study. However, this sampling technique can be widely used to conduct qualitative research, with populations that are difficult to find. Now let's explore how Snowball Sampling can be done.

➤ *Method of Collecting Data*

In the data collection method in qualitative research related to ANALYSIS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF THE OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY, HEALTH MANAGEMENT SYSTEM (SMK3) IN THE DEPARTMENT OF COMMUNICATIONS, INFORMATICS, ENGLISH AND STATISTICS, SERANG DISTRICT. Using 2 bases for data collection, namely primary and secondary data.

• *Primary Data*

Primary data collection in this research was carried out in the following way:

- ✓ Method: In-depth interviews with parties related to the section that specifically handles the SMK3 implementation program, totaling 6 informants.
- ✓ Observation method using direct observation and filling in the observation checklist sheet, by looking at the implementation of SMK3 in the company.
- ✓ Document review: Researchers use documents obtained as a complement to data that has been collected through interviews and observations. The document also provides an overview of the context of the phenomenon under study.

- *Secondary Data*

Secondary data is obtained from books, journals, theses, theses, from government data, regulations and legislation, articles or related readings and supports research which includes books related to research themes both foreign and domestic related to the implementation of safety management systems and occupational health..

- *Research Instrument*

Instruments are tools used to obtain research data. Research instruments are needed as a guide in collecting research data, both qualitative research and quantitative research.

Qualitative research places the researcher as the key instrument in the research. Other instruments such as interview guides and observation guides are supporting instruments for a researcher to collect research data. A good qualitative research instrument is one that has credibility and reliability. This is to ensure that the research results do not provide wrong information and cause misunderstandings if read by many people.

- *Qualitative Research will have a high Level of Accuracy by Following the Following Instrument Criteria:*

- ✓ *Credibility*
- ✓ *Transferability*
- ✓ *Dependability*
- ✓ *Confirmability*

- *Instrument Test*

In his various works, Norman K. Denkin defines triangulation as a combination or combination of various methods used to study interrelated phenomena from different points of view and perspectives. Until now, Denkin's concept is used by qualitative researchers in various fields. According to him, triangulation includes four things, namely: (1) method triangulation, (2) inter-researcher triangulation (if research is conducted with groups), (3) data source triangulation, and (4) theory triangulation. In the research ANALYSIS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY, HEALTH MANAGEMENT SYSTEM (SMK3) IN THE DEPARTMENT OF COMMUNICATIONS, INFORMATICS, CODING AND STATISTICS OF SERANG DISTRICT, the triangulation used by the researcher is,

- The triangulation of the method is done by comparing information or data in a different way. As known, in qualitative research researchers used interview, observation, and survey methods. To obtain the truth of reliable information and a complete picture of certain information, researchers can use free interview methods and structured interviews. Or, researchers use interviews and observations or observations to check the truth. In addition, researchers can also use different informants to check the truth of the information. Through various perspectives or views, it is expected that results are obtained by the truth. Therefore, this stage triangulation is carried out if the data or information obtained from the

subject or research informant is doubtful. Thus, if the data is clear, for example in the form of text or text/transcript of film, novels and the like, triangulation does not need to be done. However, the triangulation of other aspects is still carried out.

- Triangulation of data sources is to explore the truth of certain information through various methods and sources of data acquisition. For example, in addition to interviews and observations, researchers can use observations involved (Participant Observation), written documents, ARSIF, History Documents, Official Notes, Personal Notes or Writing and Pictures or Photos. Of course each of these methods will produce different evidence or data, which in turn will provide different views (insights) regarding the phenomenon under study. These various views will give birth to the breadth of knowledge to gain reliable truth.
- Lastly is theoretical triangulation. The final result of qualitative research is in the form of a formulation of information or a thesis statement. This information is then compared with relevant theoretical perspectives to avoid individual researcher bias in the findings or conclusions produced. Apart from that, theoretical triangulation can increase the depth of understanding as long as the researcher is able to explore theoretical knowledge in depth based on the results of the data analysis that has been obtained. It is acknowledged that this stage is the most difficult because researchers are required to have expert judgment when comparing their findings with certain perspectives, especially if the comparison shows very different results (Mudjia, 2011).

- *Data Validity*

Validity of Qualitative Research Data. In order to ensure data accuracy, researchers will carry out data validity. Wrong data will result in wrong conclusions being drawn, and vice versa, valid data will produce correct research conclusions. Alwasilah in Bachri (2010) indicates that "the challenge for all types of research is ultimately the realization of the production of knowledge that is valid, authentic, correct and ethical".

The truth or validity that must be felt is a demand that consists of three things based on Alwasilah in Bachri, (2010) "namely: 1) descriptive, 2) interpretation, and 3) theory in qualitative research". To determine the validity of the data, an examination method is required. The implementation of the data inspection method is based on a number of certain criteria. According to Bachri (2010) there are 4 (four), namely:

- Degree of trust (credibility)
- Transferability
- Dependency (dependability)
- Certainty (confirmability)

- *Data Analysis Methods*

Data originating from informants is first recorded directly by the interviewer. Conversations with informants were also recorded with the informant's permission. After that, a description of each informant obtained was made.

Notes from observations at the Container Terminal office, Operational Planning Office (KPO) and limited areas of the Container Terminal as well as a review of the SMK3 documents obtained and the recording results were refined and completed into a single writing in a transcript. Next, data analysis was carried out from the transcript.

- *In Data Analysis Techniques, Researchers Carry out three Stages of Data Analysis, Namely;*

✓ *Data Reduction*

The researcher carries out a process of selecting, focusing, simplifying, abstracting the rough data carried out in the research and organizing it in such a way that conclusions can be drawn.

✓ *Data Presentation*

Researchers present brief data in the form of an assembly of information organization that allows research conclusions.

✓ *Drawing Conclusions*

Researchers carry out activities to draw conclusions from the research results when the research ends.

- *In (Bazeley & Richards, 2000) Nvivo is a Computer Application Program used to Help Researchers Manage and Analyze Data. Nvivo is Developed by QSR International. Nvivo Helps Researchers to:*

- ✓ *Organize, Classify, and Sort Data.*
- ✓ *Examining Relationships between Data.*
- ✓ *Make Models*
- ✓ *Connecting Analysis with how to Create Models, form Models and Connect Concepts in Models.*

Each Nvivo research will be given a project name. In each project we can enter various data that we need acquired during research, making analysis, creating models, and more. In this way, all research data can be stored and collected in one location that is easy to access and manage (Sarosa, 2012).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

➤ *Organizational Overview*

The Serang Regency Communication, Informatics, Coding and Statistics Service is a regional organization which is in charge of disseminating information, developing and using information and communication technology and coding and statistics which strives for the best service to the community. The vision carried out by the Serang Regency Communication, Informatics, Encryption and Statistics Service is Advanced, Prosperous and Religious. In this case, "Forward" means being able to improve the quality of public service governance and sustainable independence of the people of Serang Regency. "Prosperous" means being able to fulfill the physical and spiritual needs of the people of Serang Regency properly. "Religious" is the embodiment of religious norms and cultural values to become a moral and spiritual foundation in fulfilling people's lives, the main thing being being able to carry out goodness and being able to prevent evil in order to become the identity of a society with noble morals.

➤ *Aspects of Bureaucratic Structure*

The bureaucratic structure aspect is a variable aspect which consists of integrated management and work instruction procedures. In this case, the indicators covering the instructions and performance procedures variables include SOPs and statutory regulations. The results and discussion regarding aspects of the bureaucratic structure at the Serang Regency Communication, Informatics, Coding and Statistics Service can be seen as follows.

Table 4 Recapitulation of Keywords Regarding Integrated Management

Category	Keywords	Amount
Integrated Management	Commitment	2
	Training	1
	Budget preparation	1
	Belum sepenuhnya sesuai	1
	Not completely appropriate	

Source: Data Processing, (2023)

Based on the results of the recapitulation of keywords related to integrated management found in the bureaucratic structure, it shows that realizing integrated management requires commitment, training, budget provision, and a gradual process. In its own implementation, integrated management in one bureaucratic structure at DISKOMINFOSATIK Serang Regency is still not fully appropriate, so in-depth studies and evaluations regarding this matter still need to be carried out.

Table 5 Recapitulation of Keywords Regarding Procedures

Category	Keywords	Amount
Procedure Work instruction	SOP	4
	Not appropriate	3
	Procedures	2
	Avoid risks	4
	Barriers to Employee Awareness	1
	Determined by the government	1

	Educational Obstacles	1
	Accident Prevention	1
	Negligence	1
	Hazard Management	1
	Stages	2
	Procedures are appropriate	1
	Important for work	1
	Minimize problems	1

Source: Data Processing, (2023)

Based on the recapitulation results of keywords related to "Work Instruction Procedures" in Table 4.4, it was found that there are 14 keywords that are related to each other. When carrying out a work instruction procedure, it is closely related to the SOP.

Table 6 Recapitulation of Keywords Regarding K3 Commitment

Category	Keywords	Amount
Commitment OSH	Top management	2
	Agreement	1
	The role of K3	1
	Obedience	1
	Educate Individuals	1
	Needs to be strengthened	1
	K3 Basics	2
	Responsible	2
	Mutation Constraints	1
	Bond/Contract	1
	Mutation Constraints	1
	Understatement	1
	Agreement	1
	minimize accidents	1
Consciousness constraints	1	

Sumber: Olah Data, (2023)

Table 7 Recapitulation of Keywords Regarding Human Resources

Category	Keywords	Amount
Human Resources Aspect	Government	1
	Top Management	5
	Builder	1
	Basic K3 Information for Policy Holders	2
	Negligence	4
	Ignorance	1
	Implementation of Kominfo Constraints on PPE	1
	Supervisor	2
	Person responsible	1
	K3 Interest	1
	Mr. Village Head	1
	Education	1

Source: Data Processing, (2023)

In the recapitulation of keywords regarding human resources, it was found that there were 15 interrelated keywords, the explanation is as follows. The government as top management is a human resource with a top position whose job is to develop the workers under it. Top management plays an important role, namely holding the policy to provide education as OSH supervisors.

In an K3 commitment there are 17 keywords has a relationship with the K3 Commitment variable. An K3

commitment is made between employees and top management through an agreement/agreement which must be adhered to as a manifestation of the K3 role. K3 commitment is needed to achieve compliance and a way to educate individuals to be responsible and not take commitments lightly. However, the commitment to K3 also has obstacles related to transfers, because workers who are transferred are generally still unfamiliar with K3, so they need to be educated so that they have a better level of awareness and are able to minimize accidents while working.

Table 8 Recapitulation of Keywords Regarding K3 Awareness

Category	Keywords	Amount
Kesadaran K3	Safety Meeting	1
	Safety Talk	5
	Toolbox Meeting	1
	Patrol	1
	Top Management	1
	Human Factors	1
	Environmental factor	1
	Tool Factor	1
	Briefing	1
	Not certified	1
	Training	1
	Rebuke	1
	Remind	1
	Evaluation	1
	Behaving K3	1
	Constrained by regulations	1
	Understand risk	1
	Difficulty in worker awareness	1
	Forced	1

Source: Data Processing, (2023)

In K3 awareness there are 19 keywords that are related to the K3 Awareness variable. K3 awareness can be raised in various ways, in DISKOMINFOSATIK itself the keyword that is most often found is safety talk, this is considered quite important and efficient in its implementation so that it can have a positive impact in the implementation of awareness on the implementation of K3 in the field and is able to minimize accidents when Work.

Table 9 Recapitulation of Keywords Regarding Facilities and Infrastructure

Category	Keywords	Amount
Facilities and infrastructure	Provider	1
	Budget	3
	PPE	4
	Active role in SMK3 Fulfillment	2
	management	2
	Data collection	1
	Checking	1

Source: Data Processing, (2023)

Facilities and Infrastructure are influenced by 7 keywords with the explanation that infrastructure is an effort by the government/stakeholders/top management to provide a budget related to the purchase of K3 equipment which includes PPE. Management has played an active role in fulfilling this. Implementation of the fulfillment of these infrastructure facilities has been achieved at 80% through data collection and checking processes

Table 10 Recapitulation of Keywords Regarding Training

Category	Keywords	Amount
Training	Back up	2
	BPBD	4
	public health Office	3
	Procurement management None	2
	K3 needs	4
	Unfulfilled	2
	Risk Management Provider	1
	Doctor	1
	First Aid	1
	Firefighter	1
	Risk	1
		1

Source: Data Processing, (2023)

Risk management and emergency response management have 12 keywords. The explanation related to risk management and emergency response management is as follows. Risk management and emergency response management at the Serang Regency Encryption Information Communication and Statistics Service is currently still not available or there is no special division to handle it. DISKOMINFOSATIK in this case is to handle risk

management and emergency response in collaboration with several related agencies, including the Health Service, BPBD. Specifically, in dealing with risks, DISKOMINFOSATIK provides doctors and first aid teams, while in supporting emergency response, DISKOMINFOSATIK also provides special firefighting teams to avoid fires in the workplace.

Table 11 Recapitulation of Keywords Regarding Reporting

Category	Keywords	Amount
Reporting	Bureaucracy	3
	P2K3	3
	Basic Evaluation	2
	Repair	1
	Management	1
	Report	1
	Top Hazard Control Management	1
	Elimination	1
	Substitution	1
	Technical engineering	1
	Administrative engineering	1
	Recap	1
Daily Report	1	
Evaluation	1	
Monthly report	2	
		1

Source: Data Processing, (2023)

Reporting must be carried out in order to fulfill the bureaucracy in P2K3. Reporting as a basis for evaluation or as an improvement in managing worker performance towards K3 in the field. The report is also submitted to top management as a basis for review of action or steps that must be taken next. In making decisions, top management can consider elimination, substitution, technical engineering and administration options as steps taken from evaluating the

results of daily reports which are collected and summarized into monthly reports.

➤ Analysis Results

After the interview results have been read, compared, grouped, then the interview results are analyzed using Nvivo 12. The transcribed interviews are then imported into Nvivo in the form of a data file with the following display.

Fig 1 Nvivo 12 Display
Source: Processed data (2023)

After inputting the interview transcript into the Nvivo application, coding is then carried out by connecting the interview text with the code that was created previously. In this research, the codes created refer to the concepts created in CHAPTER 2 which include Bureaucratic Structure, Disposition, Resources and Reporting which can be seen in the code book via Nvivo as follows.

Table 12 Nvivo 12 Codebook

Name	File	References
Disposition	0	0
Awareness	5	20
K3 Commitment	5	20
Reporting	5	15
Bureaucratic Structure	0	0
Integrated Management	5	5
Work Instruction Procedures	5	25
Resource	0	0
Risk management and Emergency Response Management	5	20
Training	5	10
Facilities and infrastructure	5	17
Human Resources	5	38

Source: Processed data (2023)

- From the Codebook results, the correlation of each code from the transcript results that have been analyzed is shown..

V. DISCUSSION

➤ *Implementation of the K3 System*

The implementation of the K3 management system has been regulated in Government Regulation Number 50 of 2012 concerning the Implementation of SMK3 which explains that an occupational safety and health management system is described as a national policy in a company which is used as a guideline for implementing and implementing K3 in all activities to guarantee and protect the safety of workforce. In this case, the implementation of the existing K3 system at Diskominfosatik includes Disposition, Reporting, Bureaucratic Structure and Resources which are explained as follows.

➤ *Disposition*

Disposition in general at Diskominfosatik has implemented the disposition and strived for it in the awareness and commitment of workers. Employee commitment plays a big role because it is the basis for starting a job that requires commitment. Workers' commitment to K3 still needs to be increased considering that workers generally underestimate the commitment to complying with SMK3 because it is considered unimportant and does not have a big impact if they do not wear K3 attributes. The crucial role of top management in K3 commitment also supports increasing workers' commitment to K3, this is based on the ability and seriousness of top management in eliminating deviations and being able to control losses caused by humans and the environment. According to Fitri (2019) there are 4 things in assessing K3 commitment in a company which include:

➤ *Participation*

Directive participation in direct interaction has been carried out by Diskominfosatik through safety talks, top management can determine "do" and "don't" in an activity.

Based on this, top management is considered active in introducing the importance of K3, apart from that, top management can be participatory by becoming a platform or supporting agent for its employees. Top management plays the role of giving advice with the aim of building the organization's HR awareness of the importance of K3 and building trust between one worker and another so that top management can create and carry out zero deviation efforts.

➤ *Providing Data Access*

In this case, top management plays a role in providing the K3 funding budget and ensuring that every worker can access information related to K3 and is funded on a priority and sustainable basis, which is a real indicator of K3 commitment. The more difficult it is for workers to access K3 information data, the lower their K3 commitment. At Diskominfosatik Serang Regency safety talks have been carried out and evaluations have also been delivered by top management in order to assess the capabilities of Diskominfosatik workers and employees in order to overcome potential K3 problems.

➤ *Learn from Mistakes*

The willingness to learn from mistakes and the desire to find the roots of the success of the K3 program is a form of top management's commitment to workers to increase the importance of K3 to workers. This treatment can take the form of constructive motivation so that workers realize the importance of K3. At the Serang Regency Diskominfosatik, there are still many workers who are afraid of regulations rather than the possible impacts, so this must be anticipated by changing the strategic approach to workers in the field.

➤ *Fokus Focus on the Process*

The willingness to learn from mistakes and the desire to find the roots of the success of the K3 program is a form of top management's commitment to workers to increase the importance of K3 to workers. This treatment can take the form of constructive motivation so that workers realize the importance of K3. At the Serang Regency Diskominfosatik, there are still many workers who are afraid of regulations

rather than the possible impacts, so this must be anticipated by changing the strategic approach to workers in the field.

➤ *Management Commitment*

In creating awareness, commitments expressed in the form of policies can influence workers. Regulations and attitudes are the basic influence of increasing a person's awareness regarding the importance of K3.

➤ *Implementation of K3 Procedures*

This application includes how a worker is willing to wear PPE without coercion, carrying out special work permit procedures so that the work carried out can be guaranteed, and work practices can be carried out safely. At Diskominfosatik, workers are still less aware of the importance of using PPE because they feel that using PPE only hinders work performance and speed. Top management and other employees can encourage and educate workers to reduce the potential for accidents, because if an accident occurs a company must pay compensation to the hospital, and is responsible for its workers, so this needs to be avoided.

➤ *Good Communication*

Communication at the Serang Regency Diskominfosatik has been carried out well and transparently, therefore there are evaluations, there are safety talks with workers. Top management has removed the boundaries between workers and management, in this case in the form of talking about safety talks, this approach is taken so that workers realize that many parties are harmed if workers experience work accidents and are able to think about the further impact of good communication.

➤ *Actively Involve Workers*

Top management can organize activities related to K3 and present workers about the importance of implementing K3 so that in these events, workers can play an active role and are able to increase their awareness at work.

Based on this, the disposition or role of top management as policy providers at the Serang Regency Diskominfosatik is quite active in building a good environment between workers and policy holders.

➤ *Bureaucratic Structure*

Bureaucratic structure is defined as a hierarchy that must be built in a company. In this case, the Serang Regency Diskominfosatik, bureaucratic in terms of integrated management and procedures, still needs to be reviewed and re-evaluated. This is because management wise, although the Serang Regency Diskominfosatik integration has been implemented comprehensively, managerially it has a different management segment to that in the company. Integrated management in this case still takes the form of providing infrastructure, K3 training and budget provision. The work procedures in this case have not been 100% fulfilled, this is because workers have not implemented the procedures according to instructions from the government to the fullest. According to Nisa'a's opinion (2019), it is explained that there are various types of SOPs that have been established by the government regarding K3, including SOPs

for PPE, SOPs for emergency preparedness and response, as well as SOPs for each field of work that have been regulated in the general guideline for implementing K3 by the government. Based on this, workers, employees and top management can implement the manual in real work in the field, so that procedural targets can be achieved 100%.

➤ *Reporting*

Reporting work accidents is very important and must be precise and accurate because through this reporting, companies can carry out evaluations related to preventing work accidents so that they do not happen again. Based on the Regulation of the Minister of Manpower of the Republic of Indonesia, work accident reporting needs to be carried out by each organizational body by sending a stage II work accident report to the Manpower Department Office by filling in the attached KK3, with a duration of 2 x 24 hours. This very important reporting function needs to be made by competent parties, in this case people who have K3 eligibility certification or have become general K3 Experts, so that it has a credible and objective assessment. At the Serang Regency Diskominfosatik, reporting is often carried out on a monthly basis from the department to the Ministry of Manpower, reporting is carried out with the bureaucracy and also with competent parties, namely K3 experts, this aims to enable the Diskominfosatik to review and evaluate the results obtained.

➤ *Resource*

Resources are generally defined as something that humans use or utilize for their survival. At the Serang Regency Diskominfosatik there are human resources, infrastructure (tools), risk management and emergency response, as well as training for human resource development. Serang Regency Diskominfosatik in terms of human resources, the top management and office employee segments are educated and have good awareness of K3 applications. This is based on this segment, top management and employees often conduct evaluation meetings and also training on the basics of K3. In the field worker segment, many parties are still not educated, so human resources still need to be improved for field workers regarding the importance of K3.

Facilities and infrastructure at Diskominfosatik Serang Regency are provided by top management by taking into account the standards and provisions that exist in Indonesia. These facilities and infrastructure include personal protective equipment for workers, although only 80% has been reached, fire extinguishers have been provided in each room, as well as safety equipment, so it can be concluded that the facilities and infrastructure have been met but are not yet optimal.

Another aspect of resources includes training, training is carried out with the aim that employees, workers and top management become better trained and understand the essence of K3. Top management provides training for general K3 experts, and provides education to several workers regarding the importance of K3 in the field.

The risk management and emergency response aspects function to regulate the prevention and management of risks that may occur for workers. Risk management and emergency response are prepared and planned by top management. In this case, the procurement of risk management and emergency response at the Serang Regency DiskominfoSatik is still not available and has not yet become a topic of discussion for K3. The absence of this aspect is because top management had previously coordinated with hospitals, fire and medical teams, so that emergency response risk management arrangements were still not a main issue in K3 at DiskominfoSatik.

From this discussion, implementation through disposition, reporting and bureaucratic structures is already available, but still needs to be improved to produce maximum output. In human resources, there are aspects that have not been fulfilled, namely aspects of risk management and emergency response, so in this case the Serang Regency DiskominfoSatik still needs to study K3 issues from the perspective of risk management and emergency response in order to help reduce the potential for accidents in the field.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

➤ *Based on Research that has been Carried out Regarding the Analysis of the Implementation of the Occupational Health and Safety Management System (SMK3) in the Communications, Informatics, Coding and Statistics Services of Serang Regency, the Following Conclusions can be Obtained:*

- In each implementation of the K3 management system at DiskominfoSatik, including Disposition, Reporting, Bureaucratic Structure and Resources, there are several aspects with different roles in this research, specifically in the resource aspect of emergency response management, because personally the department We don't yet have an emergency response team, but this has been anticipated by the existence of other services such as the BPBD (Regional Disaster Management Agency) and the Hospital Service, and all aspects have been fulfilled with various respective records.
- The obstacles that occur in implementing the K3 management system at DiskominfoSatik include several factors causing the non-fulfillment of SMK3 which have been discussed, namely human resources, infrastructure, integrated management, operational standards, and risk management & emergency response.
- On the implementation of the existing K3 management system at DiskominfoSatik, it can be concluded that corrective actions that can be proposed for implementation in the service are audits or checks in the field, strategic planning to make workers aware of the importance of K3, reviews from top management regarding K3, and how to respond or provide feedback. feedback from workers in the field, this is important considering the impact of work accidents.
- To get an increase in employee performance through SMK3 at DISKOMINFOSATIK, several things can be done that can encourage employee performance which are

categorized into work quantity, work quality, trustworthiness, initiative, adaptiveness and cooperation.

➤ *Suggestion*

• *Managerial Advice*

Based on the research that has been carried out regarding the analysis of the implementation of the occupational health and safety management system (SMK3) in the communications, informatics, coding and statistics services of Serang Regency, researchers can provide the following suggestions:

- ✓ Top management at DISKOMINFOSATIK can take a closer look at the SMK3 that is there, this is based on the SMK3 that exists in the company being different from that in the official department so there needs to be more review, especially integration with the official service itself, in this case it is important for top management. can understand the budget related to the procurement of PPE as a form of K3 requirements which plays an important role in protecting employees from various forms of work accidents that occur, then you can also pay attention to the importance of making employees aware of the voluntary implementation of K3, this can reduce the number of accidents and can have an impact on improving employee performance.
- ✓ For department heads, they can pay more attention to the importance of direct supervision of employees in their work. This can have a direct impact on employee awareness of the use of PPE and compliance with existing SOPs, and can also be used as material for consideration of whether there are any inconsistencies in the implementation of SMK3 at DISKOMINFOSATIK.

• *Suggestions for Further Research*

In this research, the researcher has limited bias and time, especially in interviewing sources and summarizing the results of the interview. In this research, the strategy applied is based on theory and practice which is generally carried out by tertiary institutions. Apart from this, the author also suggests that for further research, they can make quantitative-based research regarding the implementation of safety and occupational health management systems (SMK3) in government agencies. others who have a high level of danger at work, or study at internet provider companies.

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